

Milestone 32: Completion of 3rd programme revision with WP4-6 recommendation

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1 Introduction

This document represents the 'Completion of 3rd Programme Revision with WP4-6 Recommendation', a milestone (M32) of the ATMO-ACCESS project (Solutions for Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities). It reflects the collaborative efforts of distributed atmospheric research facilities to develop a pilot for a new model of Integrating Activities. The goal of ATMO-ACCESS is to establish a programme that provides access to multiple atmospheric research infrastructures, either individually or in combination.

WP7 is responsible for integrating the various access modalities and pilot programmes suggested by the other WPs into a comprehensive programme that offers physical, remote, and virtual access. This programme is subject to continuous updates to include novel Transnational Access (TNA) calls, as the aim is to strategically develop access modalities.

WP7 members designed the programme after consulting with WP4-6 leaders and the Coordination, and it was ratified by the Strategic TNA/VA Access Board (STVB).

2 Timetable and programme

Considering the recommendations received by WP4-WP6, the outline timetable and schedule (detailed in [Milestone 26](#)) are illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Revised timetable and programme for novel access rollout.

Table 1 has been ratified by the STVB and has been officially adopted as the TNA timetable and programme of ATMO-ACCESS. After consulting with WP4-WP6 leaders, it has been determined that the current approach is satisfactory, albeit requiring further testing. There has been substantial progress with WP4, 5 and 6 activities, such as WP4 and WP6 pilots' launch and the WP5 VA provision. The pilots and VA occur in parallel to and simultaneously with the access calls. The timeline and programme are also illustrated on the [project's website](#) (Table 2).

Table 2. Current timetable and programme of ATMO-ACCESS as illustrated on the project’s website (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/calls/>).

WP7 has engaged in further discussions with WP4-6 to evaluate the need for a third revision. It was decided that the initial programme was well-designed and required only minor adjustments. These refinements were mainly to accommodate the scheduling of training, VA, and pilot activities from Work Packages 4, 5, and 6, as outlined in Table 2. STVB discussed and supported these planning activities to ensure the costs were

appropriate for the available resources. Currently, the implementation is proceeding according to the original schedule of the program.